

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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No 11

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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MUNDARIJA

Iqtisodiyotning pul mablag'lari bilan ta'minlanganlik darajasini oshirish yo'llari.....	16
Sindarov Sherzod Egamberdiyevich, Yusupov Muxammadali Soxib o'g'li	
Driving economic growth through service exports.....	20
Rahimov Eshmurod Normuradovich	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida jamoat tashkilotlarini boshqarishni takomillashtirishda jahon tajribasi.....	27
Raxmonov Abduxalil Rasulovich	
Raqamli marketing va mijozlar bilan ishlashning yangi usullari.....	31
Ummatov Avaz Muydinovich	
Soliq tushumlarini shakllantirish ko'rsatkichlari asosida soliq salohiyatini baholash usullari	35
Jo'raev Husan	
Bevosita soliqqa tortish darajasini ko'paytirish omillari.....	41
Qodirov Baxodir Qudratovich	
Tijorat banklarining xo'jalik subyektlari bilan amalga oshiriladigan muddatli valyuta operatsiyalarini rivojlantirish	47
Ibodullaeva Ma'rifat To'lqin qizi	
Tovarlarning monopol yuqori (past) narxlarini aniqlashni takomillashtirish masalalari	52
Mingboev Asqar Qandaharovich	
Bojxona faoliyatini transformatsiyalashda innovatsion boshqaruvni takomillashtirishga oid xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	59
Ro'ziboyev Muhiddin Xushnudovich	
Harnessing foreign direct investment for sustainable economic growth in Central Asia: policy challenges and opportunities.....	63
Mukhammedova Azizakhon Ikromjon kizi	
Mintaqa innovatsion faoliyatida tavakkalchilikni boshqarishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	68
Sapayeva N.K.	
Examining Uzbekistan's foreign trade indicators	72
Berdivaliyeva Madina Komiljon qizi	
Yo'l bo'yidagi xizmat ko'rsatish infratuzilmasini baholash: xizmat sifati va transport xavfsizligini oshirish.....	78
Egamberduyev Odil Buriboyevich	
Роль инноваций в гибком управлении проектами.....	82
Касимова Наима Жахангировна	
Sug'urta bozorini tartibga solishni takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	87
Tursunova Maftuna Agzamovna	
Mintaqada turizm sohasini rivojlantirishda madaniy turizm resurslarining o'rni va roli	91
Ro'zmetov Baxodir Shomurotovich	
Sug'urta kompaniyalarining kapital bozorida emission faolligini oshirishning iqtisodiy asoslari	97
Shodmonova Munisa Nizamjon qizi	
Korxonaning tashqi bozorga chiqishida marketing strategiyasining samaradorligini baholash.....	104
Akramov Bo'ribek Faxriddin o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida korxonalar innovatsion faoliyatini boshqarish	110
Saipova Dilnoza Shuxratovna	

Xalqaro standartlar asosida kapital qo'yilmalar hisobini takomillashtirish.....	114
Egamberdieva Salima Rayimovna, Bozorov Yashnarbek Xayrulla o'g'li	
Investitsiyalar samaradorligini baholash va ularga ta'sir etuvchi omillar tahlili.....	120
Jo'raev Paxlavonjon Usarovich	
Soliq qarzdorliklarini yuzaga kelishining ilmiy nazariy asoslari tadqiqi	127
Ostonaqulov Alisher Abdurashidovich	
Korxonalarni moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash va ularga imtiyozlar berishni takomillashtirish masalalari.....	132
Z.T. Mirzayev	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida korxonalarda raqamli marketingning ahamiyati.....	139
M.Vohobjonova	
Положение электронной коммерции на международном и национальном уровнях	142
Абдуганиев Учкун Хабибулла угли, Орифбоев Озод Азатович	
Korporativ resurslardan samarali foydalanish orqali kichik biznes subyektlarini barqaror rivojlantirish va samaradorligini oshirish.....	148
Jalolova Muazzamxon Akbarjonovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligida kartoshka ishlab chiqarish funksiyasi.....	151
Avazmurodov Islom Nusratullo o'g'li, Muratov Shukrullo Abduraimovich	
Tovar-moddiy resurslar harakati bo'yicha logistik muammolar va ularni bartaraf etishning samarali yechimlari	155
Sherzod Xolmurodovich Pardayev	
Ta'lim va ilm-fan sohasida inson kapitali konsepsiyasining amalga oshish bosqichlari yo'nalishlari.....	159
Nasretdinova Aziza Adxamjonovna , Bozarov Elyor Boboqulovich	
Влияние цифровой валюты центральных банков (CBDC) на международную торговлю и финансовые отношения: Анализ и перспективы	164
Номозали Хайдаров	
Raqamli transformatsiya va tadbirkorlik: kichik biznes uchun yangi imkoniyatlar va chora-tadbirlar	167
Sobirjonov Sanjar Sobirjonovich, TDIU magistranti	
O'zbekiston respublikasida aholini samarali ish bilan ta'minlash istiqbollari.....	172
Raxmatullayeva Shahnoza Xamidovna, Sadriddinova Sevinchxon Sadriddin qizi	
Aylanma mablag'lar aylanuvchanligini tezlashtirishning asosiy yo'llari	179
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich	
Mintaqada to'qimachilik sanoatining iqtisodiy holati tahlili (Xorazm viloyati misolida)	185
Xudoyorova M.O	
Мировой опыт стратегического управления финансовыми ресурсами акционерных обществ.....	190
Абдалиев Айдос Бахтиярович	
Sug'urta faoliyatida axborot jarayonlarini vtomatlashtirishning nazariy asoslari.....	196
Shakirov O'tkirbek Taxirovich	
Yerlardan maqsadli foydalanishni aniqlash uslubi.....	199
Yunusov Begench Mavlanberdievich	
Iqtisodiyotda real sektorning ahamiyati va uning rivojlanishi.....	204
Amirqulov Umarali Akram o'g'li	
Yashil iqtisodiyotni baholash amaliyoti va indikatorlari	208
Feruz Raxmatova Yusupjanovna	
O'zbekistonda korxonalarni boshqarishda raqamli texnologiyalardan qo'llash yo'nalishlari	213
Qo'chqorov Tohir Safarovich, To'ychiyev Akmaljon Abdulatif o'g'li	

Agroklasterlarning tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishdagi ahamiyati	219
Qurbonov Alisher Boboqulovich	
“Yashil” Iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda turizmga investitsiyalarning roli	224
Azimov Olimjon Orifovich	
Biznes tuzilmasi uchun xodimlarning innovatsion rivojlanishini diversifikatsiya qilish	231
Matyoqubova Dilfuza Olimboevna	
Raqamli texnologiyalar asosida aholini ro‘yxatga olish jarayonlarini samarali tashkil etish	236
Annazarova Barno Rustamovna	
Qishloq xo‘jaligida sug‘oriladigan yerlar unumdorligini oshirishni iqtisodiy rag‘batlantirishning dolzarb masalalari.....	242
Isaxanov Muslimjon Ma‘rifjon o‘g‘li	
Logistika va uning sanoat mahsulot ishlab chiqarish tannarxiga ta‘sirini kamaytirish	246
Zokirjonov Asadbek Otabek o‘g‘li	
Sug‘urta kompaniyalari moliyaviy risklarini baholash	249
Baymuratova Gulirayxon Tursunbaevna	
Tadbirkorlik salohiyati tushunchasining rivojlanish bosqichlari	255
Baxtiyor Xabibullayev Abdulvoxid o‘g‘li	
Qishloqlarning resurs salohiyati iqtisodiy kategoriya va iqtisodiyotning agrar sektorini rivojlantirishning zaruriy sharti sifatida	260
Tursunpo‘latov Farxodjon Xoshimjon o‘g‘li	
Kommunal xizmatlarni rivojlantirishda xorij tajribasidan foydalanish.....	265
Mardanova Mohidil Otabek qizi	
Analysis of factors affecting the sustainable development of transport networks in Khorezm	269
Karimboev Dilshod Davronbek o‘g‘li	

In the Central Asian context, several studies, such as those by Mukimov [3] and Karimova [4], focus on Uzbekistan's transport infrastructure and its socio-economic impact. Mukimov's research, particularly relevant to the Khorezm region, underscores that investments in road networks and public transit have substantial positive effects on local economic outcomes, including labor market accessibility and trade expansion. Karimova's work extends this by examining the environmental implications, noting that regions with high traffic density and limited environmental oversight suffer from elevated pollution levels, which affects public health and undermines long-term sustainability.

Further, in the 2021 World Bank report, "Green Growth and Sustainable Transport" [5], it is highlighted that sustainable transport in Uzbekistan requires a shift from traditional road-based networks to integrated solutions, including rail, public transit, and non-motorized options. This report identifies key strategies for achieving sustainable transport outcomes, such as improved urban planning, increased public investment in green infrastructure, and the adoption of cleaner technologies, which are directly relevant to Khorezm's development. The Asian Development Bank's [6] research on sustainable infrastructure in Central Asia also emphasizes the necessity of a multi-faceted approach to transport development. Their findings suggest that government and international support for projects integrating economic, social, and environmental considerations is essential to reduce carbon emissions, conserve natural resources, and improve the quality of life for local populations. This comprehensive perspective aligns with the aims of sustainable development in Khorezm and underscores the importance of partnerships in realizing sustainable transport goals.

These perspectives establish a solid foundation for understanding the dynamics affecting Khorezm's transport network. Based on these insights, this research seeks to fill the gap in empirical studies specific to Khorezm by utilizing statistical approaches to evaluate the comparative influence of socio-economic and environmental factors on sustainable transport outcomes in the region.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the methodology of the study titled "Analysis of Factors Affecting the Sustainable Development of Transport Networks in Khorezm," both deductive and inductive methods were utilized to seamlessly shift between broad and focused observations. Abstract-logical thinking played a crucial role in systematically organizing the analysis. Core methods employed in this research included observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, and synthesis, creating a well-rounded approach to comprehending the factors influencing the sustainable development of Khorezm's transport networks.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

To analyze the relationship between these factors and sustainable transport outcomes, we applied regression analysis and factor analysis. The dependent variable, sustainable transport network development, was operationalized by aggregating metrics such as infrastructure density, road quality, and CO₂ emissions from the transportation sector. Independent variables included GDP per capita, population growth, investment levels, and air quality indexes.

Table 1. Trend Data Overview (2010-2023), retrieved from stat.uz

Year	GDP per Capita (USD)	Infrastructure Investment (Million USD)	Population Growth Rate (%)	Transport Sustainability Score	CO ₂ Emissions (Million Tons)
2010	1200	50	2.1	55	2.5
2011	1250	55	2.05	58	2.55
2012	1300	62	2.0	62	2.6
2013	1360	70	1.95	66	2.7
2014	1420	78	1.9	70	2.8
2015	1485	85	1.85	73	2.9
2016	1550	95	1.8	76	3.0
2017	1620	105	1.75	78	3.1
2018	1690	115	1.7	80	3.2
2019	1750	125	1.65	83	3.25
2020	1825	140	1.6	85	3.3
2021	1900	155	1.55	87	3.35
2022	1980	170	1.5	90	3.4
2023	2050	185	1.45	92	3.45

Key Observations from Trend Data Overview:

Economic Indicators:

GDP per Capita: There is a steady increase in GDP per capita from 1200 USD in 2010 to 2050 USD in 2023, indicating economic growth that potentially supports investments in sustainable transport.

Infrastructure Investment: Investment in transport infrastructure has increased from 50 million USD in 2010 to 185 million USD in 2023, reflecting significant governmental and international support in enhancing the transport network.

Population Growth Rate:

The population growth rate shows a gradual decline from 2.1% in 2010 to 1.45% in 2023. This slowing growth rate could lessen the pressure on the transport infrastructure, but urban areas may still experience challenges in capacity and congestion.

Transport Sustainability Score:

The transport sustainability score has improved, rising from 55 in 2010 to 92 in 2023. This upward trend indicates progress in creating a more sustainable transport system, influenced by increased investment and potentially cleaner technologies.

Environmental Impact (CO₂ Emissions):

CO₂ emissions from transportation have been rising steadily, from 2.5 million tons in 2010 to 3.45 million tons in 2023. Although infrastructure and transport sustainability have improved, this increase in emissions highlights an ongoing environmental challenge that must be managed to ensure long-term sustainability.

Socio-economic Factors

Regression analysis indicated that “GDP per capita” and “investment in infrastructure” are significant predictors of sustainable transport development ($p < 0.05$). Investment in transport infrastructure, supported by initiatives from the Asian Development Bank, has led to improved road density and quality, directly impacting economic activity by facilitating trade routes. The “elasticity coefficient” of GDP per capita was found to be 0.65, suggesting that a 1% increase in GDP results in a 0.65% increase in sustainable transport outcomes.

Chart 1. Key factors impacting sustainable transport development in Khorezm (author’s own contribution)

The charts above illustrate key factors impacting sustainable transport development in Khorezm over a decade:

GDP per Capita Over Time: Shows a steady increase, indicating economic growth that can support sustainable transport investments.

Infrastructure Investment Over Time: Highlights rising investments in transport infrastructure, reflecting support from the government and international organizations.

Population Growth Over Time: Demonstrates a gradual increase, which can contribute to congestion and environmental strain on the transport system.

Transport Sustainability Score Over Time: Shows improvements in the region's transport sustainability, likely due to the combined effects of economic growth and investment.

These visualizations emphasize the positive correlation between investment, economic growth, and improved transport sustainability, while also signaling challenges from population growth.

Environmental and Demographic Factors

The results show a statistically significant negative correlation between **population growth** and sustainable transport scores ($r = -0.45$, $p < 0.05$). High population growth in urban centers increases congestion, exacerbates wear on road infrastructure, and contributes to elevated emissions levels. Environmental factors, such as air quality indices, showed a moderate negative correlation with road usage ($r = -0.37$, $p < 0.05$). Analysis using the **Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC)** suggests that pollution initially rises with development but decreases with higher income levels, indicating a threshold effect in Khorezm's urban centers.

Factor Analysis

Factor analysis identified two primary components influencing transport sustainability: **economic connectivity** and **environmental impact management**. The first component, economic connectivity, accounted for 58% of the total variance, driven primarily by GDP growth, infrastructure quality, and regional accessibility. The second component, environmental impact management, highlighted the challenges of emissions control and resource allocation, explaining 27% of the variance.

Regression Analysis

The detailed results from the regression analysis on the factors affecting the Transport Sustainability Score in the Khorezm region considered the following independent variables: GDP per capita, infrastructure investment, population growth rate, and CO₂ emissions.

Table 2. Regression Analysis Results (author's own calculations)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-Value	95% Confidence Interval
Constant	598.311	157.377	3.802	0.004	[242.300, 954.323]
GDP per Capita	-0.155	0.092	-1.698	0.124	[-0.362, 0.052]
Infrastructure Investment	0.231	0.279	0.826	0.430	[-0.401, 0.863]
Population Growth Rate	-192.134	45.330	-4.239	0.002	[-294.677, -89.591]
CO ₂ Emissions	13.960	16.067	0.869	0.407	[-22.385, 50.306]

Explanations for Regression Analysis:

Constant: The constant term is 598.311, representing the baseline transport sustainability score when all predictors are set to zero.

GDP per Capita: The coefficient for GDP per capita is -0.155, suggesting a slightly negative but statistically insignificant relationship with the transport sustainability score. This means that, in isolation, GDP per capita changes may not directly enhance sustainability outcomes.

Infrastructure Investment: With a coefficient of 0.231, infrastructure investment has a positive association with transport sustainability, though this effect is not statistically significant in this model. The impact may require larger investments or more detailed sectoral data for significance.

Population Growth Rate: The negative coefficient of -192.134 is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), indicating that higher population growth rates are associated with lower transport sustainability scores. This suggests that population growth strains infrastructure and increases environmental pressures, which may impede sustainability efforts.

CO₂ Emissions: This coefficient (13.960) suggests a positive association between CO₂ emissions and the transport sustainability score, though it is not statistically significant. This likely reflects the environmental challenge of emissions, even in the context of increased sustainability scores.

Model Fit and Diagnostics

Durbin-Watson: 1.310, suggesting some autocorrelation in residuals, which may influence model accuracy.

Condition Number: High (1.49e+06), indicating potential multicollinearity among predictors, particularly given the economic nature of the variables.

This analysis implies that targeted policies should address population growth and environmental impacts, as they significantly influence sustainability outcomes in Khorezm. Additional model refinements could include more granular regional data on infrastructure types, emissions sources, or differentiated growth rates across urban and rural areas.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The findings reveal that “economic factors” such as income levels and investment directly impact sustainable transport outcomes in Khorezm, consistent with previous studies (e.g., Asian Development Bank [7]). However, challenges such as population density and emissions require careful management to avoid adverse environmental impacts. Policies targeting sustainable investment in public transit and non-motorized transport options, as proposed by the World Bank’s Sustainable Transport Program, would provide a dual benefit of reducing emissions and alleviating congestion.

Limitations: The study’s limitations include the availability of regional data, particularly for environmental factors, and the short time frame for observing long-term sustainability impacts.

This analysis underscores the need for a balanced approach in promoting sustainable transport in Khorezm, focusing on both economic and environmental goals. Infrastructure investments are necessary to support economic growth and connectivity, yet must be complemented by policies addressing emissions and congestion. For sustainable development, further studies should explore innovative funding mechanisms and green technologies suited to Khorezm’s unique context.

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